

MULTI-ACTOR Q&A

Questions and Answers for the Horizon Europe Multi-Actor Eligibility Condition

VERSION 1

PREMIERE TEAMS INVOLVED:

METK, CREA, HCC, HNEE

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CAP – Common Agricultural Policy

CSA – Coordination and Support action

CORDIS – Community Research and Development Information Service

DG – Directorate General of the European Commission

EC – European Commission

EIP-AGRI – European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability

ESR – The Evaluation Summary Report

HEU – Horizon Europe

IA – Innovation Action

IPR – Intellectual Property Rights

LLA – Living Lab Approach

MAA – Multi-Actor Approach

NCP – National Contact Point

OG – Operational Group

PA – Practice Abstract

Q&A – Question and Answers

REA – European Research Executive Agency

RIA – Research and Innovation Action

TN – Thematic Networks (special type of CSA)

ABOUT THIS BRIEFING DOCUMENT

In the regular dialogue with PREMIERE policy and project officers, the need for a Q&A document emerged in the winter of 2023/2024. It was discussed how far such a document could address the MAA-related questions that participants - in particular newcomers – commonly ask at information events about Horizon Europe funding. It was agreed that such a written contribution with answers to common questions could be useful support for upcoming information days, brokerage and training events as well as individual website visitors seeking information for the multi-actor approach (MAA).

Since Q&A documents or website sections in general are expected to provide (only) basic guidance, this reduction was also foreseen for preparing PREMIERE's Q&A document. The strengths and characteristics of a common Q&A document are its conciseness and clarity. For that reason, the authoring team decided to avoid a presentation of good practice recommendations because tips and tricks from lessons learnt are always context or call-specific results that require explanation or justification. Often, explanations for selecting certain facts or stories are diverse. Therefore, such longer explanations contradict the purpose of a simplified presentation of distinct answers to a concise question in the Q&A document. Good practices and tips and tricks for MA proposal writing will be part of the PREMIERE's other output such as the how-to-guides for MA proposal developers.

This is a living document. The results prepared so far will feed into discussions and documents, which are ongoing and will continue to evolve. In this sense, the following Q&A paragraphs represent work in progress that will be further refined and published on the PREMIERE website for dissemination and exploitation.

The document groups the questions under four headings:

- a) The MAA in general (pages 1-6);
- b) The role of EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (pages 6-9);
- c) Financial aspects of actor and stakeholder involvement (pages 9-11);
- d) Evaluating MA project proposals (pages 11-14).

Questions focusing on understanding the multi-actor approach (MAA) and the Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HEU)

1 HOW TO IDENTIFY WHETHER THE MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH IS REQUIRED FOR A HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT PROPOSAL?

The requirement for applying the multi-actor approach in a specific Horizon Europe Call is clearly stated in the Work Programme as an Eligibility condition listed under the Specific conditions of the call. Additional details may be included in the call text under the Expected Outcome and/or Scope.

2 WHAT ARE THE COMPULSORY REQUIREMENTS FOR A MULTI-ACTOR HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT PROPOSAL?

The most recent definition and specific requirements of the multi-actor approach as applied in Horizon Europe can be found in the Introduction to the current versions of a) the Horizon Europe Cluster 6 (Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment) Work Programme and b) the Soil Deal for Europe Mission in the Horizon Europe Missions and Cross-cutting Activities Work Programme.

In general terms, multi-actor project proposals must ensure the “genuine and sufficient involvement of a targeted array of actors, which serves the objectives of the topic”. A comprehensive list of potential actors is included in the Work Programme. Furthermore, “The genuine and sufficient involvement of such actors should take place all over the whole course of the project: from participation in the development of the project idea, planning and experiments to implementation, communication and dissemination of results and a possible demonstration phase.”

Following the current version of the Specific requirements for multi-actor projects in the Horizon Europe Cluster 6 Work Programme,

a multi-actor project proposal must include the following seven (7) elements that demonstrate HOW:

- the proposed objectives and planning are targeting the needs/problems/challenges of and opportunities for the (end-) users of the project results;
- the description of the project concept and in particular the composition of the consortium reflects a balanced choice of relevant key actors who have complementary types of knowledge (scientific, practical, etc.), and must ensure that project results which should be ready for practice are broadly implemented;
- the project intends to use existing practices and tacit knowledge. This should be illustrated in the proposal with a *sufficient* number of high-quality knowledge exchange activities outlining the precise and active roles of the different non-scientific actors in the work. The cross-fertilisation of skills, competencies and ideas between actors should generate innovative findings and solutions that are more likely to be applied on a wide scale;
- the project will facilitate the multi-actor engagement process by making use of the most appropriate methods and expertise;
- the project will complement existing research and best practices (its added value);
- the project will result in practical and ready-to-use knowledge, approaches, tools or products, that are easily understandable and freely accessible;
- these outputs ready for practice will feed into the existing dissemination channels most consulted by the (end-)users of the project results at the national/regional level.

In addition, multi-actor Horizon Europe projects must produce ‘practice abstracts’ in the common EIP-AGRI format. This is to facilitate more EU-wide communication related to the European Innovation Partnership on agricultural productivity and sustainability (EIP-AGRI), and the specific and cross-cutting objectives of the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).

Furthermore (where applicable), it is strongly recommended to involve partners from EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OG) funded under CAP Strategic Plans (formerly Rural Development Programmes) in Horizon Europe multi-actor projects.

3 WHAT TYPES OF HORIZON EUROPE PROJECTS IS THE MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH APPLIED TO?

Application of the multi-actor approach may be included as a specific condition for all three main types of Horizon Europe research and innovation action:

- Research and Innovation Actions (RIAs);
- Innovation Actions (IAs), and;
- Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs).

The Cluster 6 (Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment) Work Programme includes four specific types of CSA associated with Strengthening Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) which are exclusively multi-actor:

- Thematic networks (TN) as Open Calls with no pre-defined themes to compile and share knowledge ready for practice
- Thematic networks with pre-defined themes (e.g. organic farming) to compile and share knowledge ready for practice
- Thematic networks that broaden EIP-AGRI OG outcomes across borders to compile and share knowledge ready for practice
- EU advisory networks on pre-defined themes (e.g. sustainable livestock systems) that connect advisors across all EU Member States to exchange and share experiences

4 IS IT NECESSARY TO DESIGN A SEPARATE, TRANSVERSAL WORK PACKAGE FOR THE MULTI-ACTOR ACTIVITIES?

Horizon Europe project proposals that request the multi-actor approach can have a designated work package or task that ensures the application of the interactive innovation approach throughout the project's lifetime, but it is not obligatory.

Since a consequent application of the multi-actor approach pervades all dimensions of the work plan, each section of a multi-actor project proposal will document the different dimensions of the multi-actor approach. A designated multi-actor task or work package can include e.g. workshop facilitation

services, training for the use of participatory methods, dedicated internal communication strategies, co-creative stakeholder involvement concepts or systematic piloting and validation of outputs by end-users. Moreover, regular self-reflection exercises within the consortium are relevant elements of co-innovation processes, which proposal consortia can include in their methodological foundation and work plan design.

5 I'M CONFUSED BY THE DEFINITION OF THE TERMS: ACTOR, (END-)USER AND STAKEHOLDER IN THE HORIZON EUROPE WORK PROGRAMME. WHAT IS THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THEM?

Actors are individuals/persons or organisations taking part in project activities and contributing to project outcomes. A multi-actor project ensures the genuine and sufficient involvement of a targeted array of actors, which serves the objectives of the topic. The actors in multi-actor proposals or projects include: i) researchers, ii) farmers or farmers' groups and associations, iii) foresters/forestry groups and associations, vi) aquaculture producers, v) fishers/fishers' groups and associations, vi) advisors, vii) food and bioeconomy businesses, viii) other businesses, ix) consumer associations, x) local communities, xi) citizens, xii) civil society organisations including NGOs, and xiii) government representatives. The relevant types of actors, which need to join the team, differ between types of projects and expected impact. Moreover, it is important to note, that actors engage with their complementary competencies from the proposal drafting to the end of project implementation and even beyond.

Moreover, project proposals for Horizon Europe Calls that require the multi-actor approach must also present how a diverse set of stakeholders, end-users and users of the project results will be involved.

Stakeholders are individuals/persons or groups served by, affected by, or with a legitimate interest (or stake) at a certain moment in time of the project work, while (end-)users are individuals/persons who ultimately use or are intended to use a product or service, which means (end-)user of projects are putting the project results into practice.

6 IS ESTABLISHING A STAKEHOLDER ADVISORY BOARD OR STAKEHOLDER PLATFORM SUFFICIENT TO MEET THE SPECIFIC REQUIREMENTS FOR MULTI-ACTOR PROJECTS?

Stakeholder boards or platforms can be part of a project's multi-actor approach but not only. Instead, a multi-actor project is required to ensure the genuine and sufficient involvement of a targeted array of actors, which serves the objectives of the topic. The co-innovation among the project's actors should take place over the whole course of the project: from participation in developing the project idea, planning and experiments to implementation, communication and dissemination of results to a possible demonstration phase. The aim of the collaboration between the actors selected and their cross-fertilisation of skills, competencies and ideas in the project is to generate innovative and practical solutions that are likely to be applied widely by (end-)users in practice.

For that reason, the design of a stakeholder advisory board or a stakeholder platform with different relevant stakeholders engaging with the project team can be one of several measures to ensure the application of the multi-actor approach. The involvement of stakeholders from practice as representatives of different (end-)user groups can contribute substantially to reaching the project's objectives. However, it is far from sufficient on its own. More information about the co-creation of multi-actor project results is [here](#).

7 DO HORIZON EUROPE MULTI-ACTOR PROJECTS REQUIRE THE CREATION OF PRACTICE ABSTRACTS (PA)?

Multi-actor projects funded under EU Research and Innovation Programmes (Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe) as well as EIP-AGRI Operational Group projects supported under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) are required to complete the EIP-AGRI common format, which includes a project profile and practice abstract(s) (PAs).

Practice abstracts are concise summaries presenting new knowledge or innovative solutions generated by the projects, tailored for practitioners as (end-)users of the projects' outputs.

Using a common format for practice-oriented projects simplifies communication about these projects and their results across regional, national and sectoral borders. The common format gives visibility to involved actors, helps measure impact and rewards researchers' work for practice-oriented work analogous to research abstracts in peer-reviewed journals.

Each Horizon Europe multi-actor project is required to develop an 'appropriate' number of PAs in the common EIP-AGRI format. What is 'appropriate' will depend on the size and subject of the multi-actor project. Some Horizon Europe Topics call for multi-actor project proposals with statements like "as many as possible", or "as many as necessary". The idea of such requirements is to share the envisaged project results with (end-)users in an easily understandable way.

The common format allows for providing information throughout the project's lifecycle. Consortia are strongly recommended to submit the first version of the EIP-AGRI common format PAs with key project information at the beginning of the project. The idea is to facilitate networking with the EIP-AGRI/AKIS community across Europe including OGs.

PAs need to be uploaded using an online form accessible via the EU CAP Network website using the EU online platform login. More information [about EU Login is here](#) , and a detailed [Horizon Europe project user guide is here](#).

Questions focusing on the role of EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OG) in Horizon Europe multi-actor projects

8 WHO RETAINS OWNERSHIP OF THE OUTPUTS RESULTING FROM CO-CREATION IN A HORIZON EUROPE MULTI-ACTOR PROJECT?

The ownership of results arising from the co-creation processes in a Horizon Europe project is governed by the project's Grant Agreement and the customised Consortium Agreement. Together, these define the rules on intellectual property (IP) and management of results and aim to ensure that all partners' contributions and interests are fairly managed.

The Grant Agreement requires the protection and exploitation of project results, which includes ensuring that all partners involved benefit from the innovations generated. Results are defined in the Grant Agreement as any output generated by a project, such as data, knowledge, or inventions, and are owned by the partner who generates them. If results are jointly generated and the partners' contributions cannot be individually distinguished and separated, then joint ownership applies.

The default position under Horizon Europe for joint ownership is that each joint owner can use the jointly owned results independently (for research purposes) but needs consent or compensation to commercialize or transfer them. However, multi-actor consortia can define specific rules for joint ownership in the Consortium Agreement and are encouraged to do so where high levels of co-creation are anticipated. This is especially important to address the fair treatment of non-research participants (e.g. citizens, NGOs, SMEs) that are a critical part of the co-creation process.

9 DOES IMPLEMENTING THE MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH IN HORIZON PROJECTS REQUIRE THE INVOLVEMENT OF EIP-AGRI OGS?

An Operational Group (OG) may include various actors from European Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), including farmers, foresters, researchers, advisors, businesses, environmental groups, consumer interest groups or other NGOs. OGs aim to advance innovation in agriculture, forestry and rural areas in a defined spatial area. More than 3,400 EIP-AGRI Operational Groups have been established since 2014, and over 6,600 OGs are planned for the period 2023-2027.

The implementation of the MAA in Horizon projects does not require the involvement of EIP-AGRI OGs funded under the CAP Strategic Plans (former Rural Development Plans) unless explicitly mentioned in the Call Topic text. However, where applicable, it is strongly recommended that consortia involve members of interactive innovation groups, such as EIP-AGRI OGs, as they can enhance the required genuine and sufficient involvement of the (end)-user.

In the 'Scope' section of some MAA project Call Topics, the recommendation to involve OGs is specifically highlighted based on the need a) to capitalise and

build on outputs of relevant EIP-AGRI Operational Groups and/or b) to provide details on how further synergies will be built with future OGs or other interactive innovation groups operating in this context.

10 DO EIP-AGRI OPERATIONAL GROUPS ALSO APPLY THE MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH?

Yes, they do – but on a different scale and using a slightly different terminology. In contrast to Horizon Europe research and innovation projects, which are large-scale and transnational involving a minimum of three Member States (but usually many more!), EIP-AGRI Operational Group projects are significantly smaller local/regional/national innovation projects, which seldom (with a few exceptions) work across national borders.

Nonetheless, both types of projects apply the same ‘open innovation’ concept based on the interactive innovation model, which “enhances the collaboration between actors to make best use of complementary knowledge with a view to spreading solutions ready for practice”. In accordance with Article 127(3) of the CAP Strategic Plan Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, “the interactive innovation model has three key principles:

- a) developing innovative solutions focusing on farmers’ or foresters’ needs while also tackling the interactions across the whole supply chain where useful;
- b) bringing together partners with complementary knowledge such as farmers, advisors, researchers, enterprises or non-governmental organisations in a targeted combination as best suited to achieve the project objectives, and;
- c) co-deciding and co-creating all along the project”.

11 IS THE MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH SIMILAR TO THE LIVING LAB APPROACH?

Since the concept of ‘Living labs’ first emerged in the 1990s, they have been used in many different formats in a variety of sectors across the world. In a rural context, Living labs can be broadly defined as initiatives, in which research/experimentation is conducted on real farms, forests, landscapes, and others, in specific territorial and community contexts, with farmers and other actors involved from the beginning as equal partners with scientists in proposing ideas, testing them, improving them and promoting them further.

The European Commission DG AGRI has programmed the use of Horizon Europe funding to support the Living lab approach for driving long-term multi-actor collaborations and accelerating innovation in two specific initiatives: the Soil Deal for Europe Mission and the Agroecology Partnership. Several individual Horizon research and innovation projects have also chosen to use the Living lab approach for experimenting and testing solutions with diverse actors living and working in real-life situations.

Living labs are, therefore, a form of the multi-actor approach that has been adapted for specific applications and purposes within Horizon Europe.

CAP-funded EIP-AGRI Operational Groups are rather more distinct from Living labs. Whilst both build on the multi-actor approach, Living labs significantly extend the dimensions of the multi-actor approach in terms of time (beyond the short timeframe of a project), place (involving multiple sites) and content (often transdisciplinary, including a Social Sciences and Humanities component). Nonetheless, they remain highly compatible, and Horizon-funded Living labs are expected to cooperate with EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (where applicable) to promote the involvement of key local stakeholders in Living lab activities and/or in disseminating solutions.

Questions focusing on aspects related to the financial administration of multi-actor projects

12 HOW TO REMUNERATE THE ACTIVE INVOLVEMENT OF PRACTICE-ORIENTED ACTORS IN MULTI-ACTOR PROJECTS?

There is no one standard model for the financial remuneration of practitioners in multi-actor projects. The type of financial involvement depends on the degree of actors' involvement, and the needs or financial capacities of the different individuals/organisations.

Horizon Europe offers a variety of administrative rules for the remuneration of project participants. These financial rules apply to academic and non-academic partners similarly. However, some of the financial support mechanisms are more suitable for practice-oriented actors than others because

these actors might have less experience in EU-project administration or lack the administrative capacities to comply.

The highest level of integration for non-academic partners in a multi-actor consortium is the involvement as full partners in the project proposal and – in case of funding – in the Grant Agreement. A full partnership is a convincing concept for the application of the multi-actor approach. However, other forms of financial remuneration such as the involvement of Third Parties, Subcontractors or ‘Other Direct Cost’ contractors can also be appropriate given the individual needs, administrative limitations or role of the particular actor or stakeholder in the work plan. If chosen, these three funding models are part of the proposal’s financial plan. They are often also negotiated during the Grant Agreement Preparation before the project starts. While Beneficiaries (full partners) and Third Parties appear by name in the Grant Agreement already, subcontractors and contractors will be selected during the ongoing project work. Such contractual arrangements will follow the public or private procurement rules of the consortium partner in charge of their involvement.

When a Call Topic text offers the opportunity to apply the funding measure of the so-called Cascade Funding, the proposal consortium will have the opportunity to apply an advantageous model for the remuneration of actors, which will be selected and involved under simplified contractual arrangements in the project.

13 WHAT IS THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN COSTS FOR THIRD PARTIES, SUBCONTRACTING AND OTHER GOODS AND SERVICES?

Third Parties are affiliated entities, which have a legal or financial relationship with the beneficiary and participate in the project with similar rights and obligations as the beneficiaries but do not sign the Grant Agreement and therefore do not become beneficiaries themselves.

Subcontracts concern the implementation of dedicated action tasks. Subcontracted private persons or legal entities sign a contract with one of the Beneficiaries and are assigned a specific project activity to achieve the objectives. The selection of Subcontractors takes place during the project (not before). The Beneficiary has to demonstrate compliance with the ‘best value

for money' principle and the absence of a conflict of interest. In contrast, contracted services provide support under the supervision of the Beneficiary responsible for the specific project activity. Contracts fall under Other Direct Costs for Goods and Services.

The National Contact Points in all EU Member States provide detailed information and topic-specific advice. An EU-wide contact list is [here](#).

14 ARE THERE ANY FUNDING PROGRAMMES AVAILABLE FOR THE PREPARATION OF MULTI-ACTOR PROJECT PROPOSALS?

For the preparation of a multi-actor project proposal, applicants do not receive financial support from the Horizon Europe Programme. However, some EU Member States offer so-called Seed Funding schemes. These programmes are country-specific and can address all types of applicants or target exclusively e.g., applied research organisations, SMEs or EIP-AGRI Operational Groups. Please, contact your national or regional agencies for further information.

Questions focusing on the evaluation of multi-actor project proposals

15 HOW IS THE MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH BEING EVALUATED?

The application of the multi-actor approach in project proposals is a so-called eligibility condition highlighted in those Call topic texts that expect applicants to fulfil the particular requirements associated with the MAA. This and the other eligibility criteria are basic requirements, which are obligatory to be eligible for funding.

Since the multi-actor criterion requires a thorough study of the entire proposal text, the group of external experts are requested to address also the multi-actor eligibility condition when evaluating the proposal text against the expectations outlined in the Call Topic text. Applicants must convince the reviewing experts by showing how their project will meet the seven key requirements for the multi-actor approach in case of funding.

The expert's assessment of the multi-actor approach refers to all sections of the proposal text: 'Excellence' with objectives and methodologies, 'Impact' addressing communication, dissemination, exploitation and stakeholder involvement, and 'Quality/efficiency of the Implementation' covering the work plan, distribution of responsibilities, project management and decision making. The assessment also covers the multi-actor requirement of 'appropriate funding' for the various types of actors involved with their complementary competencies and facilities to be used for the planned project activities.

There is no standard evaluation model because scope and expected outcome as well as particular requirements mentioned in the call topic text vary. Overall, proposals should emphasise inter- and transdisciplinarity and showcase the complementary knowledge (scientific and practical) available in the consortium. The specific methodologies or tools and the concrete activities ensuring multi-actor co-creation are expected to deliver an application of the multi-actor approach throughout the lifetime of the project. The participatory and co-innovative methods apply to the project's multi-actor setting and the involvement of external stakeholders.

The distribution of evaluation scores depends on the specific requirements outlined in the Call Topic text and the shortcomings or weaknesses identified by the reviewers. The need to address certain requirements in the different sections of the given proposal template applies to the multi-actor approach and to the other requirements outlined in the Call Topic text. All EU Member States have National Contact Points for the funding schemes of Horizon Europe, which provide information on Call Topics.

16 WHAT TYPE OF GUIDANCE IS PROVIDED TO EVALUATORS TO ASSESS THE MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH IN PROJECT PROPOSALS?

The EC provides a range of support material and resources for evaluators (also called 'reviewers' or 'experts') who assess the proposals submitted to EU funding programmes. The support material and resources are designed to ensure that evaluators develop a thorough understanding of the evaluation criteria, processes, and the specific requirements associated with the particular

call topic. Such briefing includes the application of the multi-actor approach. More information on the evaluation process is available [here](#).

Key support measures for reviewing experts include:

- [Evaluator briefings](#): Before the evaluation sessions, evaluators receive detailed briefings providing up-to-date information on the specific Call Topic for proposals, including any thematic priorities, the MAA requirements, and the assessment of the innovation potential. Briefings often cover practical details on the evaluation process such as confidentiality, conflict of interest, and the use of the evaluation tools provided by the EC.
- Evaluation grid: Alongside videos and individual briefings, evaluators can access a comprehensive set of documents and guidelines. These materials include detailed descriptions of the evaluation criteria, scoring guidelines, and examples of successful proposals. The evaluation grid is the most relevant of these materials. It details the aspects to be evaluated based on the general structure of the proposal template. Moreover, this includes specific indications concerning the topic to be evaluated.
- Support videos for evaluators: These videos aim to guide evaluators through the evaluation process. They offer insights into the criteria, methodologies, and expectations for assessing proposals. The videos focus on specific aspects of the proposal (e. g. Open Science, Social Science and Humanities, etc.). However, a Horizon Europe video explaining the eligibility condition of the multi-actor approach is not available.

17 WHERE CAN I FIND INFORMATION ABOUT PAST AND ONGOING HORIZON MULTI-ACTOR PROJECTS

Horizon Europe evaluators are expected to assess if proposals are ‘beyond state-of-the-art’. Consequently, applicants need to show how the project proposal builds on scientific results available to date and experiences from earlier projects in this thematic field.

The easiest way to find information on past and ongoing multi-actor projects is to look at the [EIP-AGRI project database](#). This database has a filter that offers the search by ‘*type of projects*’. When searching for ‘*multi-actor projects*’, a list of all multi-actor projects appears that received funding from the precedent Framework Programme Horizon 2020. The search function also works for

‘Thematic Networks’, which represent a specific form of multi-actor projects. These projects collect existing knowledge and good practices on a given theme and aim to make this available in easily understandable formats for (end-)users such as farmers, foresters, advisors and others.

Another option to find information about ongoing Horizon Europe multi-actor projects is to search the CORDIS project database. Although this database does not offer a filter on multi-actor projects, many projects include the term ‘multi-actor’ as a keyword. When entering ‘multi-actor’ into the search function, projects and information on various multi-actor projects appear.

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